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Structural particularities of RC frame structures with wide rectangular columns highlighted through nonlinear analysis

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Abstract. High-rise residential buildings ($22 \text{ m} < \text{buildings' height} < 36 \text{ m}$) represent an architectural-engineering performance model that optimizes the ratio between the percentage of occupied land and the utility of the space built. Designing residential buildings with a structural system composed of reinforced concrete (RC) frames with wide rectangular columns (WRC) is a challenge accepted and met by engineers. This type of structures can allow a prefabrication percentage of the structural elements up to 70% (only the columns and the slabs are cast in place). Another advantage is represented from the architectural point of view by the absence of the inner corners, which cannot be avoided in case of classical columns. Such buildings were designed and erected in Iași, Romania in the 1980s, in accordance with the calculation models and regulations of that period. The paper presents the analysis of an existing high-rise residential building with WRC by response spectrum (RS) and Time-history analysis (THA). A set of artificial accelerograms was generated based on earthquakes recorded at the site. The numerical model was chosen to match the input data used for the initial calculation of the structure. The results show that these types of buildings are stiffer than traditional framed structural systems and that under the action of major earthquakes the possibility of failure is high. The results have been compared with the current requirements of the standards highlighting the performance and weaknesses of these structural systems. The aim of the research is to identify vulnerabilities for rapid and targeted response in the event of a major earthquake.

1. Introduction

Considering the continuous need for dwelling in urban areas and, the constant interest in environmental protection, understanding and optimizing residential buildings with high degree of prefabrication represents an important research direction. The positive environmental impact of prefabricated buildings has been highlighted in various studies [1-3]. In terms of CO₂ emissions, lower values were obtained, in some cases reaching 37% of the emissions recorded in case of buildings built entirely "in situ". On the other hand, when considering adaptability [4] and taking into account the life cycle of buildings [5], it becomes essential to analyse the structural behaviour of existing buildings. There are a wide variety of structural systems that are used in high-rise reinforced concrete structures, namely: reinforced concrete (RC) frames, structural walls, composite or precast systems. The article chooses to focus only on buildings with RC frame structural systems with WRC that fall into the category of high-rise residential buildings (with a total height between 22 m and 36 m).

Considering current requirements regarding environmental protection, design methods that take into account the life cycle of buildings, the implications of the sustainability and adaptability, but also fundamental structural requirements such as durability, safety and industrialization, several architectural designs were explored in order to obtain the most suitable residential project. In this direction, in Iasi, one of the typical projects designed starting with the 1970s, was a residential building with basement, ground floor and 8 story, on a structural system of RC frames with WRC [6]. One of the main feature of this project is the absence of corners in the interior (due to the fact that column members, brick walls and beams have the same thickness) spaces that occur in classical framed buildings due to the fact that the columns are the result of the intersection of "L" shaped wide rectangles for corner columns, "T" shaped for marginal columns and "cross" shaped for central columns Figure 1, a., b., c. presents the

typical shapes used, where b represents the width section, $b \geq 25\text{cm}$, while h represents the length section, $h \leq 3b$ and $h \geq 22,5\text{cm}$.

An important aspect is the high degree of industrialization (approx. 70%), due to the percentage of prefabricated structural elements used: beams, perimeter walls, floor slabs (Figure 2); this conducts to material economy, savings in cement and steel consumption between 10% and 20%.

The shape of the columns provides increased lateral stiffness, resulting in small deformations and therefore smaller vibration periods.

Figure 1. Types of columns used in RC frame structures with WRC.

Figure 2. Typical floor arrangement.

Figure 3. Existing buildings in Iași (Romania) with structural system made of RC frames with WRC.

Experimental tests carried out on scale models for RC frame buildings with WRC have concluded that the displacements for this structural system are approximately 55% smaller than for conventional frame systems and 65% larger than for structural systems with structural walls [6].

Although such constructions have been built a lot in Iasi, Romania as can be seen in Figure 3 and have benefited from a series of experimental tests that have highlighted the benefits of such a structural system, they have not been developed at a national or international level. This is one of the reasons why an analysis in line with the actual norms [7-8] is desired in order to validate or not this type of structural system and to investigate various methods for rapid intervention that can be used in case of serious damage during a major earthquake.

2. Case study

The analyzed building was designed by ICPRM - Iași (project number 8270, version C4e1), and it is categorized as a residential building with commercial spaces on the ground floor. The height of the ground floor is equal to 3.25 m and the height of the floors 1 to 8 is 2.80 m. A technical floor is located above the 8th floor. At this stage of the research, the following type of elements are considered for structural analysis: WRC and beams - modeled with bar type finite elements, floors - modeled with membrane type finite elements and elevator shaft - modeled with wall type finite elements. This choice of elements was made in order to comply with the data used in the initial design of the structure, according to the P100-81 standard [9]. The main differences between the standards developed in 1986 and the one developed in 2013 are summarized in Table 1.

Numerical simulations were performed (linear static, nonlinear dynamic) by means of ETABS software, supplemented with the program SEISMOMATCH for the artificial accelerograms and associated response spectra.

Table 1. Comparison between coefficients used in design (1981 vs. 2013).

	Importance factor (γ_I)	Peak ground acceleration (a_g)	Dynamic coefficient (β)	Reduction coefficient ($\psi=1/q$)	Behavior coefficient ($q=1/\psi$)
P 100-81	1.00	0.20	2.00	0.225	-
P 100-1/2013	1.00	0.25	2.50	-	4.44

2.1. Geometrical characteristics/ Geometric parameters/ Input data

The model shows no symmetry on either of the two axes, x-y (Figure 4), therefore torsion is expected to occur in the first vibration modes. The columns have the shape shown in Figure 4, with the following dimensions: $b = 30$ cm and $h = 60$ cm on the ground floor and $b = 25$ cm and $h = 62.5$ cm on floors 1-8; beams are 30x70 cm over the ground floor and 25x60 cm over floors 1-8. The thickness of the slab is 15 cm. The properties of the materials used are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Material proprieties.

	Elastic modulus E [MPa]	Compressive concrete strength f_{ck} [MPa]	Minimum yield strength σ_y [MPa]	Minimum tensile strength σ_t [MPa]
PC 52	210000.00	-	355.00	510.00
B250 (C16/20)	29000.00	16.00	-	-

Figure 4. Current floor layout

For the response spectrum analysis, the following parameters were used according to P100-1/2013 [7]: $\beta_0=2.5$; $T_B=0.14$ s; $T_C=0.7$ s; $T_D=3$ s; $a_g=0.25g$; $q=4.44$.

2.2. Time history input data

In addition to the modal analysis with static response spectra, a dynamic THA was also performed using the direct integration method of time-domain equations of motion. The input data for the THA was based on recorded earthquakes at the site. The earthquakes referred to in this paper are summarized in table 3 [10-11], and the characteristics of the accelerograms recorded at Iași are presented in table 4 and figures 5-7. NS and EW represent the north-south or east-west earthquake direction.

Table 3. Characteristics of Vrancea Earthquakes.

Earthquake date	Earthquake code	M_{GR}^a	Coordinates	
			Lat. N	Long. E
1986, Aug 30	861	7.00	45.53	26.47
1990, May 30	901	6.70	45.82	26.90
1990, May 31	902	6.10	45.83	26.89

^a M_{GR} – Gutenberg – Richter magnitudes.

Table 4. Peak ground acceleration of Vrancea Earthquakes recorded in Iași (station IAS3^a Lat. N: 47,193; Long. E: 27,562).

	861	901	902
a_{max} (m/s ²) -NS	0.67	0.96	0.49
a_{max} (m/s ²) -EW	0.99	1.64	0.53

^a Recorded accelerograms have been provided by NIEP (National Institute for Earth Physics) and INCĐ URBAN-INCERC institute

The selection of these accelerograms is considered optimal because the peaks of the response spectra fall in the TB-TC range [10] (Figure 8) which is more suitable for sites with small corner periods. At the same time, the method of generating accelerograms compatible with a spectrum of target accelerations (nonstationary processes) has the advantage that features of the original accelerogram, such as significant duration and phase angle, are preserved [12]. Finally, the matching between accelerograms and site response spectra must be a priority for the structure response to make sense [13]. Accelerograms were reduced to a 20 s interval.

Figure 5. Ground acceleration (m/s^2 vs s) for 30.Aug.1986 earthquake recorded in Iași (IAS3 station)

Figure 6. Ground acceleration (m/s^2 vs s) for 30.May.1990 earthquake recorded in Iași (IAS3 station)

Figure 7. Ground acceleration (m/s^2 vs s) for 31.may.1990 earthquake recorded in Iași (IAS3 station)

Two sets of compatible artificial accelerograms were generated for each recorded accelerogram, so that they correspond to the elastic response spectra for Iași, Romania. The centralization of the peak ground accelerations for the obtained 12 generated accelerograms are given in Table 5, and the accelerograms and associated response spectra are centralized in Figures 9-10.

Table 5. Peak ground acceleration^a for artificial accelerograms.

	861_artif1	861_artif2	901_artif1	901_artif2	902_artif1	902_artif2
a_{max} (m/s^2) -NS	2.50	3.33	2.36	2.93	2.81	2.51
a_{max} (m/s^2) -EW	3.44	3.32	2.56	2.75	2.32	2.82

^a *artif1* are generated with ETABS and *artif2* are generated with SEISMOMATCH

Figure 8. Elastic response spectra for Iași (RO) vs recorded spectra.

a. NS components

b. EW components

Figure 9. Artificial accelerograms used for THA.

Figure 10. Elastic response spectra for Iași (RO) vs recorded spectra.

3. Results and discussion

From the modal analysis results with response spectra, of interest at this stage of the research, are the eigenmodes of vibration and the displacements.

Table 6 shows the values of the period of vibration for the first 6 eigen modes as well as the participation ratios associated with each mode on X and Y direction respectively, and the torsion, RZ. Although building asymmetry is a good indicator to assume a large degree of torsion in the first eigen mode, this effect does not occur. One of the reasons could be that the shape of the columns has the advantage of a proper material distribution with moments of inertia having values 30-40% higher than those of equivalent classical columns, resulting in higher stiffnesses on the two directions [6].

Table 6. Periods of vibration and modal participation ratios.

	T [s]	U _x	U _y	R _z
Mode 1	0.917	0.663	0.049	0.046
Mode 2	0.879	0.084	0.550	0.134
Mode 3	0.762	0.006	0.178	0.592
Mode 4	0.273	0.108	0.011	0.007
Mode 5	0.267	0.017	0.093	0.012
Mode 6	0.237	0.002	0.014	0.101

Regarding the displacements, the results of the static analysis according to P100-1/2013 [7] indicate that they are exceeded by values between 1% and 22% at intermediate levels (floors 3-6). However, these are four times higher than the results of experiments performed for scaled buildings in the '80s [6].

The causes of these differences may be the fact that in this paper the model of the RC building with WRC, does not take into account, the exterior prefabricated walls. It is expected that the presence of this type of elements to change the fundamental mode of vibration and lateral displacements of the building [14].

Recent studies show that scale ramp modeling influences the results of structural analysis [15-16]; the effect of ramps was not considered in this paper.

An important effect on the stiffness of the structure is the effect of the interior partition walls [17-19]; these structural elements will be included in the calculation in the further developments of the model.

The Hilber-Hughes-Taylor (HTT) method [20] of integrating the equations of motion, with parameter $\alpha = -1/24$, was used for the THA. The seismic loading was considered as bidirectional (the EW component of used earthquakes was applied along X axis of the model while the NS component was applied along Y axis) for each of the generated artificial accelerograms.

The displacements resulting from the nonlinear analysis are up to 25% larger than the values resulting from the static analysis (see figure 11); the explanation may be, on the one hand, the chosen value for the behavior factor q (which in this case was kept to correspond to the one originally designed according to P100-81 [9]) and, on the other hand, the cause may be found in the response spectra of the selected compatible accelerograms, which have, in some cases, values up to 30% larger than the elastic response spectra at the site.

Regarding the base shear force, a significant difference between the results obtained by THA and the results of the static analysis is observed, up to 70% (see table 7); the cause may also be the choice of the behavior factor q , but also the behavior of the structure in terms of stiffness - these aspects will be detailed in the next research on this topic.

The rotation of the plastic joints is exceeded (see figure 12, a.-f.); this aspect will be developed in the following studies as it is the main source of information in establishing rapid intervention measures in case of major earthquakes.

a. displacements – x dir.

b. displacements – y dir.

Figure 11. Displacements.

Table 7. Base shear force.

	Static	861_artif1	861_artif2	901_artif1	901_artif2	902_artif1	902_artif2
F_xmax (kN)	3133.32	8667.32	9531.49	9370.76	8893.51	10346.70	9055.92
F_ymax (kN)	3029.07	8248.05	9770.80	8443.25	8414.11	10272.00	10197.00

a. 861_artif1

b. 861_artif2

c. 901_artif1

d. 901_artif2

e. 902_artif1

f. 902_artif2

Figure 12. Formation of plastic hinges (last step).

4. Conclusions

This paper represents the first stage in the study of existing buildings in frames with WRC and presents the results obtained from THA. The aim is to validate the necessity of constructing residential buildings with a high degree of prefabrication and to identify the vulnerabilities of the existing buildings.

Following the analysis of such a building realized in the 1980s, it is found that they are vulnerable to the seismic actions regulated by the current norms, and the displacements are higher than the allowable ones. However, these results need to be validated by numerical modeling with shell-type elements and by taking into account the interior and/or perimetral walls.

Given the differences in the base shear force, the next stages of the research will perform a nonlinear static pushover analysis to identify the displacement requirements of the structure and analyze the compliance with current norms in terms of reinforcement percentages.

Potential failure mechanism points have been identified through the global THA and will be investigated in a more detail manner using computational programs are which able to capture local effects.

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